
Research

Impact of Social Responsibility on Corporate Performance: Case Study of South Africa's Retail Chain Company

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Abstract: This paper studies the relationship between social responsibility and corporate performance. This study investigates how a South African retail chain company interact with stakeholders, and how this in turn affects the company's revenue and customer loyalty. This study will use a qualitative content method to analyze how the company interacts with its stakeholders and how the interactions between the company and its stakeholders affects the overall company's performance. This study examines the expectations of the stakeholders of Pepkor Holdings limited, determines the extent to which the company meets these expectations, and uses corporate performance indicators to evaluate the relationship between stakeholder treatment and company performance. This study used the secondary data collected from the company report. The results show that customers' decision-making is not only influenced by the characteristics of typical retailer (such as brand), but also by intangible resources (such as corporate social responsibility, corporate image and ethical business practices). In addition Consumers expect more from companies than affordable prices, good quality and convenience. Engaging in social responsibility activities gives a company competitive advantage. Therefore, in order to win the trust and loyalty of customers, companies should not just abide by the law. The company must determine the specific ways to create value for different stakeholders. Since promoting positive stakeholders' relations has a positive impact on the company's performance, companies need to adjust their own values so that their interaction with stakeholders can ensure mutual benefits. In practice, retail companies must determine how to integrate social responsibility into their corporate strategy in a way that maximizes value created for all stakeholders. The study will complement earlier studies on CSR activities in South Africa, which were not conclusive on the relationship between stakeholder engagement and firm performance. This will also contribute to further studies on this topic, which will continue to explore the positive relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate performance.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Corporate Performance, stakeholders, retail chain company, social policies

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Introduction

Background of the study

According to the agency theory, owners of a company are stewards that manage the funds given by clients, who are shareholders, and expect to use the funds to create value through profit maximization. Today's world presents a more complex corporate structure which is different from the traditional structure. That is to say, in addition to the owners and shareholders, there is an additional group of individuals who can directly or indirectly influence the operation of the company or be influenced by it. Traditionally, the company's main objective is to create value and maximize profit. Economic responsibility has been the primary goal for corporations (Friedman, 1962). However, for the past two decades, the company has faced a wider range of responsibility, including the responsibility to the environment and the local communities. It's worth noting that it is not enough to be environmentally friendly and serve the community. Companies should also conduct their business in an ethical way. This is the so-called corporate social responsibility. Elkington (1999) describes CSR as the summation of corporation three responsibilities namely economic, social and environmental responsibility. Godfrey and Hatch (2007) define corporate social responsibility as an activity outside the traditional business scope of a company, which is done for the benefit of the society, not required by the law. Rue and Byars (1993) sum it up well. They defined corporate social responsibility as non-mandatory corporate behavior, rather than the result of pressure groups, public opinion or legal demands.

Statement of problem

The business processes of companies cannot be separated from interactions with the environment and the society. Companies need to be accountable for their actions that harm the environment or violate human rights. Owen (2007) believes that companies should consider how their business operations affect economy, society and environment. With the increasingly close connection of the world, global issues such as climate change, pollution, waste management and poverty cannot be ignored. Therefore, the concept of corporate social responsibility is not only concerned by scholars, but also paid attention by the governments and companies. Although a majority of African countries are in better economic conditions than they were in the past decades, the current economic development has resulted in countless social and environmental problems. Although countries are facing the same problems, they are affected by these problems in different degrees, so corporate social responsibility could mean different things for different communities. The purpose of this study aims to determine what CSR means for an African retail chain company by analyzing its corporate social responsibility initiative.

Objective of the study

The purpose of this study is to understand the nature of CSR practices in a retail company in South Africa. The purpose of this study is to establish a relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate performance. This study will explore if corporate social responsibility is indeed an investment, which will ultimately be rewarded in terms of increasing sales, brand loyalty and business sustainability.

Significance of the study

Except for the multinational companies operating in Africa, there is little research on the relationship between social responsibility of African companies and corporate performance. This study attempts to continue the existing literature in this field by studying the extent to which social responsibility of active stakeholder participation contributes to positive corporate performance. The structure of the rest of this paper is as follows: the next section reviews the key theories of corporate social responsibility, the third section briefly analyzes the corporate social responsibility activities of the South African retail chain company, and the fourth section briefly describes the methods adopted and findings. The study gives insight into the nature of CSR in African retail chain company. In addition, it shows companies the

importance of incorporating corporate social responsibility actions. Understanding the importance of corporate social responsibility activities to corporate performance will help companies to develop moral practices and social policies for the benefit of society and companies.

Literature review

In this chapter, critical literature is reviewed. The overall goal of this study was to determine the relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate performance. The main issues reviewed in this chapter include the concept and theories of corporate social responsibility, and the significance of corporate social responsibility.

Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate social responsibility may be described as a method of corporate decision-making including social and environmental factors. Harpreet (2009) defined corporate social responsibility as a company voluntarily taking public interests into its decision-making, and abiding by the triple bottom line of 'the people, the planet and profit'. Becchetti, giacomo and Pinnacchio (2005) defined corporate social responsibility as the goal that companies choose to pursue the maximization of shareholders' interests in accordance with the laws and regulations. According to McWilliams and Seigel (2001), CSR is more than just following the law. The business operations of the company have both positive and negative impacts on society and the environment. According to Dimitriades (2007), the company must accomplish two tasks at the same time, that is, maximize its positive effects and minimize its negative effects on the external environment. According to Gray and others (1987), corporations have an obligation to communicate the environmental and social effects of their business operations to particular interest groups within the society. Tirole describes corporate social responsibility as a management design that seeks the internalization of stakeholders' benefits.

Companies hold different views on corporate social responsibility. Some consider corporate social responsibility as mere a moral obligation to society, without expected return. Others consider CSR as a strategic tool, which could make them gain competitive advantage and earn more profits. However, others view CSR as a moral requirement necessary for environmental protection and sustainability. These underlying differing perspectives may explain why companies undertake different types of CSR activities, with some emphasis placed on issues in the community, whilst others focus on the environment. In addition, others pay attention to the labor force or market-related corporate social responsibility, while others emphasize the compliance with business ethics and standards.

The existing literature on corporate social responsibility in Africa shows that the motivation of companies is mainly the moral obligation to meet social needs, and their corporate social responsibility activities are mainly philanthropic, focusing on community development (Baughn, Bodie & McIntosh 2007; Blow field & Frynas 2005; Chapple & Moon 2005; Ofori & Hinson 2007). Although corporate social responsibility in Africa is mainly philanthropic in nature, corporate social responsibility activities of other companies also come from other motives. Okeyo (2004) found that companies participate in corporate social responsibility activities in order to gain publicity, gain competitive advantage and respond to social needs. Ofori, Nyurr and Dako (2014) found that banks in Ghana consider corporate social responsibility practices as a strategic tool. The motivation for banks to implement corporate social responsibility stems from desire for profitability and sustainability. In addition, although there is a positive relationship between social responsibility and financial performance, the financial performance of Ghana Bank does not significantly depend on its corporate social responsibility practices, but on other control variables such as growth, sources, debt ratio and scale.

Theories of corporate social responsibility

1. Classical theory

Friedman (1970) believes that under a free market system, the only responsibility of a company is to utilize resources and participate in profit maximization activities in compliance with laws and regulations. In short; "business of business

is business" (Friedman, 1970). According to this theory, economic efficiency is the main criterion to measure corporate performance. This theory overestimates the costs incurred by social responsibility and underestimates the explicit benefits (cost savings, resource productivity) and implicit benefits (good corporate reputation, customer loyalty and trust) of CSR. There is nothing wrong with profit being the main goal of a company, but it cannot be the only goal. Moreover, social responsibility is not incompatible with profit making. On the contrary, the only sustainable way to do business is to be socially responsible.

2. Social Contract Theory

Social contract refers to the implicit and explicit agreement among the main stakeholders in the society, namely the government, companies and people. The basic premise of social contract theory is that there is a relationship among people, companies and the government. According to Jean (1762), for the better functioning of society, every individual agrees to give up a certain degree of freedom and rights. Social contract is widely used to explain the relationship between company and the society. Companies are responsible for the society in which they operate.

3. Stakeholder theory

Social contract theory is the foundation of the stakeholder theory. Founded by Freeman (1984), this theory has been recognized by other authors, including Porter (1980), Donald and Preston (1995) and Jones (1995). According to stakeholder theory, an organization is not only an entity that acts for a specific purpose, but a coalition of different interest groups. A company is responsible for creating value for all stakeholders. The company exists not only to serve the interests of shareholders, but also to serve the interests of other groups or individuals who have interests in the company, including customers, suppliers and employees. Other stakeholder groups include the government, society and the local community. The success of a company depends on how the company interacts with stakeholders. In other words, cultivating mutually beneficial relationships with stakeholders is crucial to the sustainability of the company. The concept of stakeholders extends to include the environment as a stakeholder. This is based on the premise that the organization's activities will affect the external environment.

Significance of Corporate social responsibility

Positive relationship between social responsibility and corporate performance

There have been many previous studies that empirically tested the relationship between social responsibility and corporate performance. The first empirical finding links social responsibility to positive business performance. People are not only interested in the kind of business corporations have but also how they do business. In other words, people are not only interested in the explicit value created by companies in providing goods and services, but also interested in the implicit value rooted in how companies create such value. Andrew, Luo and Fang (2014) used the role of discount prices to determine the relationship between ethical values and consumer responses. They found out that consumer's perception of firm brand is influenced by the firm's ethical values. The results of Brunk research also pointed out the correlation between corporate ethics and brand awareness. Brunk believes that consumers expect the companies to contribute to society. Soloman and Hansen (1985) found that the indirect costs of CSR actions can be offset by the improvement of employee morale and productivity. Pava and Krausz (1996) observed that there was a positive correlation between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Ruf and others (2001) found that change of corporate social responsibility brought financial benefits in the form of increases of sales and growth of returns on capital. Simpson and Kohers (2002) recorded the positive correlation between social and financial performance of banks.

More empirical studies have proved the positive relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance, showing the two aspects of this relationship. First of all, corporate social responsibility strengthens the positive relationship between the company and its stakeholders, and reduces the company's expenses, thus increasing accounting profit. According to Albinger and Freeman (2000), corporate social responsibility leads to profit, because a

company that implements corporate social responsibility has the ability to attract and retain the desired workforce. Dolan (1997) supports this point by referring to Forbes' report, which found that more than half of the 2,100 MBA students expressed their willingness to take job with lower pay in a socially responsible company. Therefore, there is a positive correlation between corporate social responsibility and corporate reputation, and corporate reputation is an important driving force of the company's financial performance.

Roberts and Dowling (2002) also found the substantial and positive relationship between corporate reputation and financial performance. Peloza (2006) and Gardberg and fombrun (2006) found that corporate image is an important intangible asset, which provides a vital link between social responsibilities and financial performance by reducing transaction costs and improving brand loyalty. Ofori and Hinson (2007) concluded that the strategic management of corporate social responsibility often produces positive results, such as financial performance and organizational effectiveness. Hahn and Scheermesser (2006) also revealed that the practice of corporate social responsibility not only generates new income, but also protected the existing profit rate. Coelho, McClure and Spry (2003) pointed out that the way companies interact with their stakeholders has a direct impact on profitability. Pearce and Robinson (2009) explain further that turning a blind eye to society's concerns may be profitable in the short term but detrimental to the long run sustainability of business.

The existing literature on corporate social responsibility in Africa also supports a positive relationship between corporate social responsibility and company performance. Akanbi and Ofoegbu (2012) conducted a case study of United Bank for Africa (UBA) in Lagos, and verified the positive impact of corporate social responsibility on corporate performance, including financial performance and non-financial performance, such as employee morale and good corporate image. Omwenga (2012) tested the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance of companies listed in Nairobi Stock Exchange. He found that CSR brought positive financial performance, such as the increase of return on assets and sales. He concluded that companies should focus on corporate social responsibility in order to achieve better financial performance. Another study by Obusubiri (2006) tried to establish the relationship between corporate social responsibility and portfolio performance in Nairobi Stock Exchange. He found that there was a positive correlation between corporate social responsibility and portfolio performance, and companies with the highest ranking of corporate social responsibility perform better than the companies with the lower ranking of corporate social responsibility.

Negative relationship between social responsibility and corporate performance

The second group of documents support the negative correlation between corporate social responsibility and corporate performance. Preston and O'Bannon (1997) argue that managers tend to reduce expenditures on social performance in order to increase short term profits and personal compensation. However, when the company's performance is not good, the spending on social projects is used as a means of diverting attention. Waddock and Graves (1997) assert that corporate social responsibility may have a negative impact on financial performance due to the indirect cost of carrying out corporate social responsibility activities.

No relationship between social responsibility and corporate performance

The third group of theorists found that there was no relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Waddock and Graves (1997) believe that the neutral relationship between social responsibility and financial performance can be attributed to the fact that there are many variables related to financial performance of companies, which makes the connection between social responsibility and financial performance coincidental. Nelling and Webb (2009) believe that although a strong performance of the stock market has led the company to make considerable investment in the corporate social responsibility of employee relations, the activities of corporate social responsibility do not affect financial performance.

Double-side relationship between social responsibility and corporate performance

Green and Foxall (1997) contend that there is a double-sided relationship between social responsibility and corporate performance. They believe that better financial performance will bring better corporate social performance, that is to say, only when companies take the first step to achieve their main goal (profitability), can they begin to assume social responsibilities. On the other hand, the positive relationship with stakeholders proves that good corporate social responsibility will bring better financial performance. The latter view is based on the fact that corporate social responsibility will affect people's view of companies.

Conclusion

These theories provide different perspectives to judge and observe the company's activities and performance. These theories emphasize an important point, that is, companies have other responsibilities to society and its stakeholders, which go beyond economic, technical and legal requirements. The survival and long term sustainability of organizations depends on identifying groups or individuals with interests in their activities and engaging with them effectively. Corporate social responsibility can increase profit by improving corporate reputation, inducing brand uniqueness and increasing sales and income. In line with previous literature (Brammer et al. 2006; Fiori et al. In 2007), this study adopted four social performance indicators: interaction with the local community and charities, attitude towards the customers, employee treatment and concern for the environment.

Analysis of the Pepkor's CSR activities

This study investigated how Pepkor, a South African retail company, complied with the country's corporate social responsibility policy. This study utilized a qualitative content analysis data collection method, which emphasizes the qualitative nature of the data, rather than the quantification of data. This method provides an opportunity for collecting and analyzing information about corporate social responsibility. In this study, corporate social performance indicators are used to determine whether corporate social responsibility activities are successfully implemented. The company's social performance indicators used include: Participating in local community and charity, attitude towards the customers, employee treatment and environmental protection. This study used the second qualitative data collected from the company CSR report of 2019-2020.

Corporate overview

Pepkor is a retail chain company based in South Africa with business interests in Africa, Poland, Australia, United Kingdom, Romania, New Zealand and Slovakia. The main business operations include clothing and general merchandise, furniture, appliances and electronics, building materials and Fintech.

Fig. 1: Pepkor group segmental revenue distribution

Source: Pepkor 2020 CSR report

Pepkor’s Corporate social responsibility

Pepkor henceforth, PEP creates value through business operations and interactions with its stakeholders. Products and services are the main output of the company. Customer satisfaction shown by the continuous purchase of the company's products ensures the continuous revenue stream needed by the company's growth and sustainable development. The main goal of Pepkor is to promote active stakeholder relations. The company stakeholders are composed of groups or individuals who can significantly influence or be influenced by the company's business activities, its outputs or results, or their behavior can affect the company's ability to create value over time. Pepkor’s total contribution to the corporate social investment was 40.7 million rand, equivalent to 2.6 million dollars. Whereas 14.2 Rand million in product donations were made by all retail brands to support local charities in their areas.

1. Environment

With the aggravation of global concerns about climate change, companies must reduce the environmental impact of their business operations. One of the ways they can do that is by reducing their carbon footprint. In order to do this, companies must monitor and report their carbon emissions. The following is the carbon footprint report of Pepkor.

Table 1: Pepkor 2020 carbon footprint report

Carbon footprint	Tones CO2e
Total carbon footprint	308856
Total scope 1(fuel)	49156
Total scope 2(electricity)	259700

Source: Pepkor 2020 CSR report

According to the corporate standard of GHG Protocol, company's green gas emissions fall into three categories. Scope 1 consists of direct emissions from company’s core facilities including company logistic infrastructures. While scope 2 are firm's indirect emissions from generation of purchased energy. Scope 3 includes all indirect emissions related to the company's operations, but it is not included in scope 2. Both scope 1 and 2 are mandatory to report while scope 3 isn't because it's hard to monitor. According to table 1, scope 2, electricity is the largest contributor to the total emission of Pepkor, accounting for 85% of total emissions. Scope 1 fuel emission accounted for only 15% of the total carbon footprint and mainly from 34% diesel and 6% petrol consumption. Pepkor's logistics function is centralized, so that the company can save fuel, because a truck transports the inventory of various brands in one place. Another way that Pepkor reduces its impact on the environment is by recycling water and plastic bags for packaging. All PEP plastic bags are made from post-consumable plastic waste, saving 1000 tonnes of plastic from landfills. Pepkor's clothing stores re-uses clothes hangers. In the furniture department, most products are received, stored and distributed in the original packaging provided by manufacturer.

2. Customers

The company's goal is to treat their customers with respect and dignity, and make products and services accessible to all customers. Through direct communication online or offline, the company can understand the needs of customers. The company has an online platform mainly for customer feedback concerning their products and services they provide. Customer feedback can help the company to make necessary product and service improvements. Customer expectations can be summarized as follows: Affordability, quality, availability, diversity, customer service, and trustworthy and responsible brands. This company offers the best products at the most affordable price. Pepkor has earned for itself the title "97% Best price leadership". The presence of poor transport infrastructures makes accessibility to products hard for residents in rural areas. Pepkor has the hugest rural footprint of any clothing retail in South Africa, with more than

half of its stores being located in rural areas. This customer-centered approach has improved the trust and loyalty of customers and brand awareness. In 2019, Pepkor won the best rating in the South African Customer Satisfaction Index. Pepkor is one of the most popular brands in Africa, with over 20 million known customers at present.

3. Employees

Employees are an important factor for organizational success. Under proper treatment and quality guidance, employees can help reduce costs and bring more profits and income to the company. Pepkor provides employees with a safe and high-quality working environment, so that they can not only achieve career development, but also achieve personal growth. Last year, 37.9 million Rand was spent on employee training and development. Employees' expectations are as follows: Competitive financial compensation, jobs that can develop their skills and abilities, promotion opportunities, safe working environment and an organizational culture that is conducive to the growth of employees. The company meets these expectations by implementing the decentralization strategy, through which employees and the leaders of their respective departments can directly contact each other. Moreover, with training programs, conference meetings and the company whistle-blowing hotline, the company is made aware of staff management issues as well as areas for improvement. In addition, of 63.7 billion Rand of income, 6.5 billion Rand, or 10.2% of the income, is used for employee compensation. Good employment treatment improves employee morale, which is proved by the employee turnover rate of only 16%. The employment Equity Act No 55 (EE) was established in 1998 with the aim to ensure equality and fair treatment at the workplace. Another similar but more specific agenda was introduced in 2003, called the Broad-based Black Economic Empowerment Act 53 (BEE Act) in an attempt to address the inequalities suffered by black South African citizens as a result of the apartheid regime. Pepkor's actions are guided by the requirements of EE and BEE Acts. The company has a total of 50,000 employees among which 94% are black with 3% being top managers.

4. Regulators, legislations and government

Profitability is the key to the growth and development of companies. However, the main question is not how much profit companies make, but how they make it. Pepkor ensures that their business practices comply with ethical standards and industry, regulatory and legal requirements. Some of Pepkor's regulators are the Johannesburg Stock Exchange and Prudential regulation authority. These measures ensure that Pepkor abides by laws and regulations, conducts business in an ethical manner, participates in national priorities and invests in activities that benefit the community. Pepkor scored 85% for corporate governance compliance against the FTSE/JSE Responsible Index.

5. Communities

Poverty, child malnutrition and health problems are one of many problems that perplex communities in the developing countries. Pepkor's motto is "Give back to the community". The company has undertaken various projects to help the communities by improving people's living standards. In order to help the community better, a company need to know the real needs of the community. Through the daily interactions between employees and customers, awareness of community needs is generated. Each business chooses the most suitable method of social interaction, and the nature of their connection to local communities. The community's CSR activities can be summarized as follows: Response to Covid-19, investment in education, cooperation with Non Profit organizations and donations.

For most companies and governments, 2020 was probably the worst year. At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, Pepkor made substantial donations that helped to stimulate immense national relief efforts. Pepkor partnered with strategic organizations that had group-wide and national reach and together with the local government helped alleviate the impact of Covid-19 on the people. Employees have initiated community-based projects and reached out to the most vulnerable and affected people. In addition, Pepkor diversified its production facilities to produce reusable fabric masks, disposable protective clothing for donations and customers, screens and disinfectants.

Pepkor's education initiative, PEP Academy was established in 2008. PEP Academy provides a quality environment for children's education. During the pandemic, PEP launched a home-learning program that provided learning opportunities in low technology environments. Pepkor donated more than 5,000 family study packages that ensured the continuity of education during the lockdown period. Another education initiative is one called "Ububele school" that was established in 2015. This initiative focuses on improving the physical environment, training teachers and empowering parents to support informal learning at home.

Flash, a technology company of Pepkor, supports a non-profit organization called Smile Foundation, which helps children with different types of cleft palate. The foundation not only provides funds for surgery, but also helps to improve the quality of life of many poor families in South Africa. Flash also supports the development of medical team skills by investing in training programs and funding medical equipment. JD Group, a furniture retailer, is one of the subsidiaries of Pepkor and supports a non-profit organization called the Click Foundation. The foundation cooperates with technology brands to help learners improve their ability to use technology at school and home. Everyone is entitled to safe and better living environment. Pepkor's construction company provides building material support for children's families and schools.

Findings

This study investigated the influence of social responsibility on company performance. The research adopted a stakeholder-centered approach, focusing on how Pepkor meets the needs of its stakeholders, and how this in turn affects the company. The findings indicate positive effects from corporate socially responsible initiatives such as brand popularity, employee morale and good image. The other important perspective involves the reputation of the company. Given that products in the retail industry are similar, a company that engages in CSR can establish credibility and reputation, thereby distinguishing itself from others that do not engage in CSR. The results just show the relative impact of CSR activities. That is to say, engagement in CSR may result in better corporate performance. The results show that corporate social responsibility has dual management meaning for retail companies, which is not only a feasible business strategy to create goodwill, but also a positive brand image, which may bring positive corporate performance results to retail companies (Sonali & Linda ,2012).

Recommendations

Companies should stop treating sustainability as a mere component of corporate social responsibility but as a business imperative. In practice, retail companies must determine how to integrate social responsibility into their corporate strategy in a way that maximizes value created for all stakeholders. This research is of practical significance to African retail chain companies. First of all, customers' decision-making is not only influenced by the characteristics of typical retailer (such as brand), but also by intangible resources (such as corporate social responsibility, corporate image and ethical business practices). Consumers' expectations of companies exceed the affordable prices, good quality and convenience. Customers are more likely to buy products from companies that engage in social responsibility activities. In order to win the trust and loyalty of customers, companies should not just abide by the law. In addition, the company must determine the specific ways to create value for different stakeholders. That will require active engagement with the respective stakeholders. Different stakeholders have different powers, so corporations' decisions regarding CSR should be managed carefully to avoid value creation for one stakeholder at the expense of another. To promote consumer awareness of the corporations' socially responsible actions, corporations should include CSR related information in their strategic marketing activities, that way they can enhance brand image.

Conclusion

In the current business environment, the company's social influence is becoming more and more important. Company performance is affected by strategic management and operations in market and non-market environments. Technological progress has increased the chances of obtaining information through the media, so companies are more influenced by public opinions and social expectations. Companies play an important role in social development, so they are responsible for social welfare. For this reason, more and more companies are trying to integrate sustainable business practices into their corporate strategy. Contemporary consumers are paying more and more attention to the influence of enterprise behavior on society and the environment. Although, there is debate about the extent to which the owners and managers of companies should consider social and environmental impacts in their decision-making. It is generally believed that the company's goal is no longer limited to maximizing profits. The only sustainable way of doing business is to maximize the value created by the company for its stakeholders.

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References

- [1] Akanbi PA, Ofoegbu OO. Impact of corporate social responsibility on bank performance in Nigeria. *US-China Public Adm*, 2012; 9(4):374–383.
- [2] Albinger, H.S. & Freeman, S.J. Corporate social performance and attractiveness as an employer to different job seeking populations. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 2000; 28(3), 243–253. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1023/A:1006289817941>
- [3] Andrews, M., Luo, X., Fang, Z., & Aspara, J. Cause marketing effectiveness and the moderating role of price discounts. *Journal of Marketing*, 2014; 78(6), 120–142.
- [4] Baughn, C.C., Bodie, N.L. & McIntosh, J.C. Corporate social and environmental responsibility in Asian countries and other geographical regions. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 2007; 14(4), 189–205. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/csr.160>
- [5] Becchetti, L., Giacomo, S., Pinnacchio, D. Corporate social responsibility and corporate performance: evidence from a panel of US listed companies. RESEARCH PAPER SERIES, Working Paper No. 78, 2005.
- [6] Blowfield, M. & Frynas, J.G. Setting new agendas: critical perspectives on corporate social responsibility in the developing world. *International Affairs*, 2005; 81(3), 499–513. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2346.2005.00465.x>
- [7] Brammer, S. Brooks, C. & Pavelin, S. Corporate social performance and stocks returns: UK evidence from disaggregate measures. *Financial Management*, 2006; 35(3), 97–116.
- [8] Brunk, K. H., Un/ethical company and brand perceptions conceptualising and operationalising consumer meanings. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 2012; 111(4), 551–565.
- [9] Chapple, W. & Moon, J., Corporate social responsibility (CSR) in Asia: A seven country study of CSR website reporting. *Business & Society*, 2005; 44(4), 415–441. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0007650305281658>
- [10] Dimitriadis, Z. S. (2007). Business ethics and corporate social responsibility in the e-economy: a commentary. *Electronic Journal of Business Ethics and Organization Studies*, 2007; 12(2). http://www.ejbo.jyu.fi/articles/0701_1.html.
- [11] Dolan, K.A., 'Kinder, Gentler M.B.A.s', *Forbes*. 1997; 2 June, pp. 39–40.

- [12] Donaldson, T., and Preston L.E., The stakeholder theory of the corporation: Concepts, evidence, and implications. *Academy of Management Review*, 1995; 20, 65-91.
- [13] Elkington, J., Triple bottom-line reporting: Looking for balance. *Australian CPA*, 1999; 69(2), 18-21.
- [14] Fiori, G. Donato, F. & Izzo, M. F., Corporate Social Responsibility and Firms Performance. An Analysis on Italian Listed Companies. <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1032851>, 2021/10/25.
- [15] Freeman, R. Edward., *Strategic management: A stakeholder Approach*. Boston, 1984; MA: Pitman.
- [16] Friedman, M., *Capitalism and freedom*. Chicago University Press, P. 133 National Development Plan 1997-2001.
- [17] Gardberg, N.A. & Fombrun, C.J. Corporate citizenship: Creating intangible assets across institutional environments. *The Academy of Management Review*, 2006; 31(2), 329–346. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMR.2006.20208684>
- [18]. Godfrey, P.C and Hatch, N.W., Researching Corporate Social Responsibility: An Agenda for 21st Century[OL]. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.459.2441&rep=rep1&type=pdf>, 2021/11/01.
- [19] Gray R, Owen D, Maunders K. *Corporate social reporting: accounting and accountability*. Prentice Hall, Hemel Hempstead, 1987.
- [20] Greenly, G.E. and Foxall, G.R. Multiple stakeholder's orientation in UK companies and implications for company performance. *Journal of Management studies*, 1997; 34, 2: 259-284.
- [21] Hahn, T. & Scheermesser, M. Approaches to corporate sustainability among German companies[J]. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 2006, 13(3), 150-165. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/csr.100>
- [22] Harpreet, S.B. Financial Performance and Social Responsibility: Indian Scenario. <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1496291>, 2021/10/25.
- [23] Hoganlovells. 2017. <https://www.hoganlovells.com/en/publications/bbbee-for-doing-business-in-south-africa>, 2021/11/01.
- [24] Jones, T. M. Instrumental stakeholder theory: A synthesis of ethics and economics *Academy of Management Review*, 1995; 20, 404-437.
- [25] McWilliams, A., Siegel, D. Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: correlation or misspecification?. *Strategic Management Journal*, 2001; 21, (5), 603-609.
- [26] Milton. F. A Friedman doctrine: The Social Responsibility Of Business Is to Increase Its Profits. <https://www.nytimes.com/1970/09/13/archives/a-friedman-doctrine-the-social-responsibility-of-business-is-to.html>, 2021/11/02.
- [27] Mitnick, Barry M., *The Theory of Agency: A Framework* (1975). In: Barry M. Mitnick, *The Theory of Agency*.
- [28] Nelling E, Webb E. Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: the “virtuous circle” revisited. *Rev Quant Financ Acc*, 2009; 32(2):197–209.
- [29] Obusubiri, M.M. A study of corporate social responsibility and portfolio performance at the Nairobi stock exchange. University of Nairobi, 2006, 17-37.
- [30] Ofori, D.F., Nyuur R.B. & S-Darko, M.D. Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: Fact or fiction? A look at Ghanaian banks. *Acta Commercii*, 2014; 14(1), Art.#180, 11 pages. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/ac.v14i1.180>
- [31] Ofori, D. & Hinson, R. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) perspectives of leading firms in Ghana *Corporate Governance. The International Journal of Business in Society*, 2007; 7(2), 178–193.
- [32] Okeyo, W.O., A survey of rationale and determinants of level of corporate social responsibility among firms in Kenya. University of Nairobi, 2004; 19-26.
- [33] Omwenga D. K. The relationship between corporate social Responsibility and financial performance of Companies listed in the Nairobi securities exchange. University of Nairobi, 2012; 16-40.
- [34] Owen, D. Beyond corporate social responsibility: The scope of Corporate Investment in Community Driven Development, World Bank Report no: 3739-GLB. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 2007, 74,363-372.
- [35] Pava, L and Krausz, J. The association between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 1996; 15,321-357.

- [36] Peloza, J., Using corporate social responsibility as insurance for financial performance. *California Management Review*, 2006; 48(2), 52–72. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/41166338>
- [37] Pepkor 2020 corporate report. <https://www.pepkor.co.za/>, 2021/11/02.
- [38] Preston, L. and O'Bannon, D. The corporate social-financial performance relationship. *Business and Society*, 1997; 36, (1), 5-31.
- [39] Porter, M.E., *Competitive strategy* Free press, 1980.
- [40] Roberts, P.W. & Dowling, G.R. Corporate reputation and sustained superior financial performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 2002; 23(12), 1077–1093. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/smj.274>
- [41] Rousseau, J. J., *The social contract, or principles of political right*. 1762.
- [42] Rue, L.W. and Byars, L.L. *Management: skills and application* 6th Edition. Von Hoffman Press Inc, USA, 1993.
- [43] Ruf, B. M., Muralidhar, K., Brown, R. M., Janney, J.J. and Paul, K. An empirical Investigation of the relationship between change in corporate social performance and financial performance: A stakeholder theory perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 2001; 32,143-156.
- [44] Simpson, W.G. and Kohers, T. The Link between corporate social and financial performance: Evidence from the banking industry. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 2002; 35, 97-109.
- [45] Soloman, R., Hansen, K. *It's Good Business*, Atheneum, New York, 1985.
- [46] Sonali, D. Linda S. Niehm. Exploring the role of values and norms towards consumers' intentions to patronize retail apparel brands engaged in corporate social responsibility (CSR). *Clothing and Textiles Research Journal*, 2017; 4(5), 17-25.
- [47] The Greenhouse Gas Protocol. <https://ghgprotocol.org/corporate-standard>, 2021/11/01.
- [48] Tirole J. Corporate governance. *Econometrica*, 2001; 69(1):1–35.
- [49] Waddock SA, Graves SB. The corporate social performance-financial performance link. *Strategic Management Journal*, 1997; 18(4):303–319
- [50] Western cape govt. <https://www.westerncape.gov.za/general-publication/employment-equity-act-summary>, 2021/10/28.

